

Coordinated power system services from distributed batteries

dBATe - Distributed battery based coordinated power system operation support concept

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Abstract—The continuous penetration of renewable energy sources (RES) in the electricity supply poses stability and quality issues for the grid. One promising and elegant solution to smooth these problems is the use of battery systems (BS). This paper describes a simple and robust concept, dBATe, for an optimised and coordinated control of multiple battery systems distributed in a power distribution system, supporting the operation of the grid through regulation of voltages and power flows in the grid.

Keywords: battery systems; coordinated operation dBATe, power distribution system; power flow regulation; voltage regulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The paper addresses possible technical impacts of smart and coordinated regulation of battery systems distributed in a low voltage (LV) electricity distribution network. A battery system (BS) consists of one or more batteries (including their battery management system - BMS), one or more AC/DC converters, and the necessary control and external communication. The AC/DC converters control the power flow between the AC grid and the internal DC bus of the battery system in both directions. The converters are assumed to be capable of providing 3-phase AC active and reactive power in both directions with individual regulation of the phases.

Any control of the operation of a battery system (BS) in the grid will affect the local voltage, the local power balance, the power flow in the power lines and the global power balance. The impacts from the operation of a battery system will be highest close to the battery. However, the aggregated impact from the coordinated operation of multiple batteries within the same grid may also have significant 'global' impact. Some impacts from a given regulation may be positive, others may be negative. For example, a regulation of the active power from a battery system may reduce the load of a specific power line, but at

the same time affect the local voltage and a global power balance in a negative way.

In order to optimise the operation of multiple battery systems (BS) in a power distribution network, it is necessary to prioritise between the various impacts. For that, a 'value indicator' (VI) has been developed.

Ideally, the impacts could be calculated through a complete load flow analysis of the grid. In this work, a more pragmatic and practical approach is proposed. A battery system in a LV grid will have an impact on:

- 1) the local voltage,
- 2) the power flow in the feeder and
- 3) the power balance at the substation

The voltage at the battery system (U_b), the power flow (including the phases balance) in the feeder at the substation (I_f), and the power balance at the substation (P_s) should therefore be monitored. The value indicator (VI) for that battery system will be based on these values.

The control of the battery system is based on the actual local voltages, the active and reactive power in the grid, current in the transformer and the knowledge of the impacts of the active and reactive power on the local voltages.

In addition, the actual impact of the active and reactive power from the battery system on the local voltages will be monitored by the battery system and the information will be used in the control of the battery system – adaptive control. This is not further described in the paper.

The proposed concept for optimized and coordinated operation of multiple battery systems (BS) in a distribution grid is called dBATe (Distributed battery based coordinated power system operation support).

Figure 1: Example of three battery systems (BS) connected in different configurations to feeders from two substations in the same MV grid. There are three kinds of meters installed, voltage and current meter (UI), current meter (I) and frequency meter (F).

II. IMPLEMENTATION

The dBATe control concept is illustrated by the following example.

Three battery systems are distributed in a low voltage (LV) grid, illustrating three different use cases (Figure 1).

The battery systems are installed as follows:

- 1) At the end of a feeder (Feeder 11) (BS #1)
- 2) Connecting two feeders from the same substation (Feeder 12 and Feeder 13) (BS #2)
- 3) Connecting two feeders from two different substations (Feeder 14 and Feeder 21) (BS #3)

In the example, each battery system includes two independent 3-phase inverters (Figure 2). Each inverter is able to control individually the active and reactive currents in each of the three phases. If two independent inverters are not required (as for the BS #1 use case), the two inverters

Figure 2: Each battery system includes a battery with its battery management system (BMS) and two individual 3-phase inverters.

can operate in parallel.

The battery systems with the back-to-back inverters can be used to control the power flow between the two external AC-connectors connectors, AC 1 and AC 2; in principle without affecting the battery state of charge (SoC).

A. The BS #1 Use Case

The battery system BS #1 is connected to the end of Feeder 11. The battery system can be used to regulate the local voltage at the position of the battery system and the current in Feeder 11; including the voltage and current balance between the three phases. The current from the battery system will also have impact on the voltages at other points in the feeder and on the current at the Substation 1.

B. The BS #2 Use Case

The battery system BS #2 is connected between Feeder 12 and Feeder 13. As for the BS #1 use case, the battery system can be used to regulate the local voltage and current in the two feeders. The battery system can also be used to transfer power between the two feeders at the position of the battery system. The current from the battery system will also have impacts on the current at Substation 1.

C. The BS #3 Use Case

The battery system BS #3 is connected to Feeder 14 (from Substation 1) and Feeder 21 (from Substation 2). As for the BS #2 use case, the battery system BS #3 can be used to regulate the local voltage and the current in the two feeders. In addition, the battery system can be used to transfer power between the two feeders from the two different substations. The current from the battery system will have impact on the current at the two substations. The power flow between the two feeders will in addition have an impact on the power flow in the medium voltage (MV) line, connecting the two substations at MV level.

Figure 3: Illustration of the regulation scheme of one of the AC currents from the battery system BS #2 for one phase. The current for each phase of the battery system (BS) will be regulated by a weighted combination of all the actual values of those variables that are affected by the regulation, relative to their critical levels and impact factors (G).

III. CONTROL

The system is intended for real time operation. The operation of the battery system (BS) will be adjusted every 1 minute based on the grid state variables. If the battery system does not receive updated information on the grid states, the battery system will only regulate its operation based on the local voltage and frequency.

In the example, the regulation of the current from the battery system BS #2 will affect the local voltage (U_{b2a} and U_{b2b}), the current in the feeders (I_{f12} and I_{f13}) and the Substation 1 current (I_{s1}) and voltage (U_{s1}). The current in each phase of the feeders for BS #2 (two three phase inverters) is therefore controlled by a weighted combination of these variables (U_{b1a} , U_{b2b} , I_{f12} , I_{f13} , U_{s1} , I_{s1} – for each phase individually). A similar control concept can be adopted for the other battery systems as well achieving independent regulation of the voltage and current of each phase.

Figure 4: All the variables are individually normalised (p.u.) so their minimum values correspond to -1 and their maximum values correspond to +1.

The variables are first individually normalised (Figure 4) and then individually weighted in two steps. First relative to how critical the actual values of the variables are (Figure 5) and then relative to the individual impacts of the battery current on the variables (the gain factor in Figure 3).

This forms the ‘value indicator’ (VI) for each of the grid state variables. All of the ‘value indicator’ values are finally summed to control the specific inverter current for one phase. This is repeated for the current in each phase of the AC inverter, for both inverters in each battery system, and for all the battery systems.

The principle ensures that if more variables are at high critical states, those variables which are most affected by a change in the regulation of the battery system will have the highest influence on the regulation of currents from the battery system.

Figure 5: The normalised values of the variables are individually weighted with a non-linear function, representing their individual criticality levels.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The dBATe concept was presented in the paper, which with a coordinated operation of distributed battery systems in a distribution grid, supporting the operation of the grid, presents a simplified and robust coordinated control of multiple battery systems that cooperate to support the operation of the grid, where and when most needed.

The optimised operation of the battery systems is based on real time measurements of a subset of the grid state variables. Any operation of a battery system necessarily results in power losses and battery degradations. The battery system is therefore only activated, when the value of its operation in the grid exceeds the cost of operation of the battery system itself.

Battery systems, distributed in a distribution grid, can support the operation of the grid, by stabilising the voltage levels and avoiding overloads of the power lines and the

transformers. Battery systems may in addition provide 'virtual inertia' (frequency support) and short circuit power in the grid, stabilising the grid in case of faults and stability problems in the grid.

The battery systems may therefore substitute other investments for the reinforcement of the grid. However, the battery systems are still too expensive to demonstrate positive business cases. But, with the continuously decreasing prices of the LV battery systems and the real time data and control communication, in combination with the multiple functions offered by the battery systems, the authors expect battery systems to play an increasing role as grid stabiliser units in the power distribution grid in the years to come.

The concept is expected to be demonstrated in real in a specific LV power distribution system in Denmark during 2019.